

Transparency, Accountability and Prosperity: Building a Better Madhesh

Dr. Satyam Prakash

Associate Professor,
Department of Biochemistry,
Tribhuvan University,
Janaki Medical College, Janakpurdham
Email: sprakashy2424@gmail.com

Abstract

The pursuit of prosperity in Madhesh requires a governance model that prioritizes transparency, accountability, and inclusive development. This study explores the role of citizen participation and effective public service delivery in strengthening democratic institutions and ensuring equitable socio-economic growth. The objective is to analyse how participatory governance and institutional reforms can foster trust, reduce corruption, and promote prosperity in the region. The research will be a mixed-methods approach. Primary data will be collected through structured questionnaires (n=250) administered to local citizens, civil society representatives, and government officials in selected districts of Madhesh Province. Focus group discussions will be conducted to capture community perspectives on governance practices, service delivery gaps, and citizen engagement mechanisms. Secondary data will be sourced from government reports, policy documents, and scholarly articles addressing governance and development in Madhesh. The study will adopt a participatory rural appraisal (PRA) framework to assess community involvement in decision-making and applied descriptive and thematic analysis to evaluate transparency indicators, accountability mechanisms, and service delivery efficiency. Expected findings might be that citizen participation through ward-level forums and local councils significantly improves monitoring of public projects, reduces mismanagement, and enhances accountability. However, bureaucratic inefficiency, political interference, and limited digital governance tools may remain barriers to effective service delivery. The need for stronger grievance-redressal systems, open budget hearings, and technology-driven platforms to ensure transparency. Strengthening citizen engagement, promoting ethical leadership, and adopting innovative service delivery models can foster trust between government and people. A citizen-

centred governance framework is essential to ensure sustainable prosperity and social justice in Madhesh, transparency and accountability are critical to building a prosperous Madhesh.

Keywords: transparency, accountability, citizen participation, public service delivery, Madhesh, prosperity